

Investigation Of Current Progress in Benzimidazole: An Emerging Framework for Cyclooxygenase Inhibitors

Sandip Chaudhari^{1*}, Bharat Jain²

¹Research Scholar, Smt. S. S. Patil College of Pharmacy, Chopda Dist. Jalgaon., KBC North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon, Maharashtra India

²Department of Pharmaceutics, Smt. S. S. Patil College of Pharmacy, Chopda Dist. Jalgaon, KBC North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon, Maharashtra India

ABSTRACT

Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory agents have long been effectively used for alleviate pain and inflammation, and continue to be a routine choice for millions of patients worldwide. Chronic inflammatory conditions create a vicious cycle, where inflammation and related pathological states, such as obesity, can exacerbate inflammation, and chronic inflammation can, in turn, promote obesity-related diabetes by inducing insulin resistance. Consequently, managing inflammation becomes crucial in all pathological conditions. Prostaglandins, catalysed by COX-I, have protective effects on the gastrointestinal tract. In this article, we discuss bioactive benzimidazole derivatives from recent years, spanning 2010 to 2025.

Keywords: Benzimidazole, Inflammation, Prostaglandin, Gastrointestinal disease, COX-I & II.

INTRODUCTION

Inflammation is an essential immune reaction that plays a crucial role in survival and helps maintain tissue balance under various adverse conditions, such as infections and tissue damage. [1]. In 1971, John Vane confirmed that acetylsalicylic acid and NSAIDs inhibit cyclooxygenase enzymes, which are responsible for converting arachidonic acid into prostanoids, thereby revealing the molecular mechanism of NSAID activity. Over time, researchers identified several drugs, including diclofenac [4], mefenamic acid [5], phenylbutazone [6],

indomethacin [7], naproxen, and ibuprofen [8], that share aspirin's mechanism of action. These drugs are also commonly referred to as "aspirin-like drugs" [9]. Traditional NSAIDs, known for their nonselective COX inhibition, are among the most widely used medications for [50] alleviating short-term fever, pain, and inflammation [10]. In medicinal chemistry, the benzimidazole nucleus is recognized as a crucial pharmacophore and a privileged structure. Recently, [11] benzimidazole has gained prominence as a pharmacophore in the design of anti-inflammatory analgesic molecules [12,13,14].

Fig.1 Structures of clinically used COX-1 and COX-II Inhibitors

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COX-I is a constitutive isoenzyme that is widely present in most cells [20]. Prostaglandins produced by COX-I play a protective role in the gastrointestinal tract. In contrast, COX-II is an inducible enzyme [21] and serves as the primary source of prostaglandins [21,22]. It is regarded by researchers as the main pathological enzyme responsible for inflammation [23]. Targeting multiple opioid (μ) receptors simultaneously offers a promising strategy for pain management. Ligands capable of this strategy paves the way for new research directions in treating complex diseases. By employing a poly pharmacological approach, one can develop new analgesics with [48] improved efficacy and lower side effects. Chronic gastritis can result in mucosal damage, and the use of NSAIDs may exacerbate this condition [29,30]. A pressing issue in addressing inflammatory illnesses is the absence of effective anti-inflammatory medications that specifically target

COX-II enzyme [31]. The benzimidazole nucleus is widely acknowledged by scientists for its versatility and is often referred to as a ‘Master Key’ due to its presence in a broad range of medicinal compounds. Altering the position of benzimidazole can improve the physical, chemical, physiological, and pharmacokinetic properties of the resulting molecules [32]. Many antifungal medications and proton pump inhibitors incorporate the benzimidazole moiety, and these pharmaceuticals have received FDA approval. Notable examples include albendazole and omeprazole [36]. Benzimidazole has shown a wide range of effects, demonstrating efficacy against various organisms and conditions such as fungi [37], helminths [38], asthma [39], diabetes [40], hypertension [41], parasites [42], bacteria, blood clots, obesity, antioxidants, tumors, and inflammation. In this review, we explore bioactive benzimidazole hybrids [3] from recent years, spanning 2010 to 2025.

Fig 2 Mechanism of NSAID

CHEMISTRY

Benzimidazole is a type of heterocyclic aromatic compound distinguished by a core structural feature [15]. This feature consists of a six-membered benzene ring [34] joined at the four & five positions of a five-membered [39] imidazole ring system. [8,9].

Fig 3. Benzimidazole Nucleus

Heating alone efficiently transforms the monoacyl derivative of OPD into the corresponding benzimidazole [41]. These transformations are typically conducted at temperatures slightly above the melting point of the initial compounds. This method

is convenient for preparing benzimidazoles when monoacyl derivatives are [28] readily available. To enhance the procedure, heat the diamine's monoacyl derivative in a nitrogen atmosphere to prevent oxidation [18]

Scheme 1. Synthesis of benzimidazole derivatives

Fig. 4. SAR profile of benzimidazole nucleus for anti-inflammatory activity

Fig 5. Structure Activity Relationship (SAR) of Benzimidazole

Fig 6. Benzimidazole derivatives Comp a, b, c

Fig 7. Benzimidazole derivatives comp 1a,1b and 1c

Fig 8. Various 2-thio-Benzimidazole derivatives

Benzimidazole Derivatives for treatment of Inflammation

Numerous authors have examined the spectrum of pharmacological effects exhibited by benzimidazole

and its derivatives [5, 6]. Benzimidazole derivatives, discussed here as analgesic and anti-inflammatory agents, influence several therapeutic targets, including the COX enzyme.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of 2-phenyl amino benzimidazole compounds

These observations led us to create and assess a novel series of benzimidazole derivatives, aiming to identify compounds with notable COX-2 inhibitory properties. [50]

Fig 9. Various 2-phenyl amino benzimidazole containing compounds (3a-3j)

Selective COX inhibitors

The main enzyme that facilitates the conversion of arachidonic acid [5] into PG and thromboxanes is COX [18,19]. Consequently, drugs that target COX-

II are considered good anti-inflammatory agents due to their gastrointestinal tolerability, and complete inhibition of COX-I is not advisable when seeking more effective and safer anti-inflammatory medications [37]

Fig 10. Newly synthesized Substituted benzimidazole compounds

CONCLUSION

Benzimidazoles have significantly influenced medicinal chemistry due to their wide range of biological activities, making them valuable hybrids for treating various diseases through different mechanisms. This review examines the research available on benzimidazoles concerning their anti-inflammatory properties from 2010 to 2025. It aims to pave the way for new research opportunities on compounds derived from benzimidazoles and to inspire medicinal chemists to investigate this promising heterocyclic in biological studies.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

Sandip S. Chaudhari designed this study, conducted the data analysis and prepares manuscript.

Bharat V. Jain have done Proof reading.

All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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